

Scalar Area Product

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1 Scalar area product

Definition 1.1. Scalar area product in \mathbb{R}^3 . Given $\underline{a}, \underline{b} \in \mathbb{R}^3$

$$\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b} := \|\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b}\|$$

Where $\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b}$ is the vector product between the two vectors.

Theorem 1.1.

$$\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b} = \sqrt{\|\underline{a}\|^2 \|\underline{b}\|^2 - (\underline{a} \cdot \underline{b})^2}$$

Where $\underline{a} \cdot \underline{b}$ is the usual scalar product between the two vectors.

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{a} \cdot \underline{b} &= \|\underline{a}\| \|\underline{b}\| \cos \theta \implies \cos^2 \theta = \left(\frac{\underline{a} \cdot \underline{b}}{\|\underline{a}\| \|\underline{b}\|} \right)^2 \\ \sin^2 \theta &= 1 - \cos^2 \theta = 1 - \left(\frac{\underline{a} \cdot \underline{b}}{\|\underline{a}\| \|\underline{b}\|} \right)^2 \\ \underline{a} \wedge \underline{b} &= \|\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b}\| = \|\underline{a}\| \|\underline{b}\| \sin \theta = \\ &= \|\underline{a}\| \|\underline{b}\| \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\underline{a} \cdot \underline{b}}{\|\underline{a}\| \|\underline{b}\|} \right)^2} = \sqrt{\|\underline{a}\|^2 \|\underline{b}\|^2 - (\underline{a} \cdot \underline{b})^2} \end{aligned}$$

□

Definition 1.2. General scalar area product. Given two vectors $\underline{a}, \underline{b} \in \mathbb{R}^n$

$$\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b} = \sqrt{\|\underline{a}\|^2 \|\underline{b}\|^2 - (\underline{a} \cdot \underline{b})^2}$$

Figure 1: $\|a\|\|b\|$, $a \cdot b$ and $a \wedge b$ form a right triangle.

Remark 1.1. Pythagoras relation.

$$(a \wedge b)^2 = (\|a\|\|b\|)^2 - (a \cdot b)^2$$

Since $\|a\|\|b\|$, $a \cdot b$ and $a \wedge b$ follow the Pythagorean theorem, they form a right triangle, visible in Fig. 1.

Remark 1.2. Properties.

- $n = 1 \implies a \wedge b = 0$

$$a \wedge b = \sqrt{\|a\|^2\|b\|^2 - (a \cdot b)^2} = \sqrt{a^2b^2 - (ab)^2} = 0$$

- Self product: $a \wedge a = 0$

$$a \wedge a = \sqrt{\|a\|^2\|a\|^2 - (a \cdot a)^2} = \sqrt{\|a\|^4 - (\|a\|^2)^2} = 0$$

- Commutative: $a \wedge b = b \wedge a$

$$a \wedge b = \sqrt{\|a\|^2\|b\|^2 - (a \cdot b)^2} = \sqrt{\|b\|^2\|a\|^2 - (b \cdot a)^2} = b \wedge a$$

- Multiplication by scalar: $(\alpha a) \wedge b = a \wedge (\alpha b) = \alpha(a \wedge b)$; $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$
- Not associative because this product is not defined between a scalar ($a \wedge b$) and a vector (c).

Theorem 1.2. *Distributive over addition inequality.*

$$a \wedge (b + c) \leq a \wedge b + a \wedge c$$

Proof. Vector product is distributive over addition:

$$a \wedge (b + c) = a \wedge b + a \wedge c$$

so

$$\begin{aligned} a \wedge (b + c) &= \|a \wedge (b + c)\| = \\ &= \|a \wedge b + a \wedge c\| \leq \|a \wedge b\| + \|a \wedge c\| = a \wedge b + a \wedge c \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 1.3. *Scalar area product as determinant.*

$$\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b} = \sqrt{\begin{vmatrix} \underline{a} \cdot \underline{a} & \underline{a} \cdot \underline{b} \\ \underline{b} \cdot \underline{a} & \underline{b} \cdot \underline{b} \end{vmatrix}}$$

Proof.

$$\sqrt{\begin{vmatrix} \underline{a} \cdot \underline{a} & \underline{a} \cdot \underline{b} \\ \underline{b} \cdot \underline{a} & \underline{b} \cdot \underline{b} \end{vmatrix}} = \sqrt{\begin{vmatrix} \|\underline{a}\|^2 & \underline{a} \cdot \underline{b} \\ \underline{a} \cdot \underline{b} & \|\underline{b}\|^2 \end{vmatrix}} = \sqrt{\|\underline{a}\|^2 \|\underline{b}\|^2 - (\underline{a} \cdot \underline{b})^2}$$

□

2 Generalized vector product

Definition 2.1. Norm function. Given $\underline{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$

$$\mathcal{H}_n : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$$

$$\mathcal{H}_n(\underline{x}) := \|\underline{x}\|$$

Definition 2.2. Reverse norm function.

$$\mathcal{H}_n^{-1} : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \{B : B \subset \mathbb{R}^n\}$$

with

$$\mathcal{H}_n(\underline{x}) = x \quad \forall \underline{x} \in \mathcal{H}_n^{-1}(x)$$

so

$$\mathcal{H}_n^{-1}(x) = \partial B_x(\underline{0}) = \{\underline{x} : \underline{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n \wedge \|\underline{x}\| = x\}$$

Proof.

$$\mathcal{H}_n(\mathcal{H}_n^{-1}(x)) = \mathcal{H}_n(\underline{x}) = \|\underline{x}\| = x \quad \forall \underline{x} \in \mathcal{H}_n^{-1}(x)$$

□

Remark 2.1. Given two vectors $\underline{a}, \underline{b} \in \mathbb{R}^3$

$$\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b} \in \mathcal{H}_n^{-1}(\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b})$$

since

$$\mathcal{H}_n^{-1}(\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b}) = \mathcal{H}_n^{-1}(\|\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b}\|)$$

Remark 2.2. Given two vectors $\underline{a}, \underline{b} \in \mathbb{R}^3$

$$(\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b}) \cdot \underline{a} = (\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b}) \cdot \underline{b} = 0$$

since

$$\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b} \perp \langle \underline{a}, \underline{b} \rangle$$

where $\langle \underline{a}, \underline{b} \rangle$ is the plane spanned by the two vectors.

Definition 2.3. Generalized vector product. Given two vectors $\underline{a}, \underline{b} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, consistent with Rem. 2.1 and 2.2, we can say that:

$$\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b} \in \mathcal{H}_n^{-1}(\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b}) \cap \langle \underline{a}, \underline{b} \rangle^\perp = \{ \underline{x} : \underline{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n \wedge \|\underline{x}\| = \underline{a} \wedge \underline{b} \wedge \underline{x} \cdot \underline{a} = \underline{x} \cdot \underline{b} = 0 \}$$

3 Triple product

Theorem 3.1. *Volume of Parallelepiped*

$$V = \underline{a} \cdot (\underline{b} \wedge \underline{c}) = \left\| \underline{a} - \frac{\underline{a} \cdot \underline{b}}{\|\underline{b}\|^2} \underline{b} - \frac{\underline{a} \cdot \underline{c}}{\|\underline{c}\|^2} \underline{c} \right\| (\underline{b} \wedge \underline{c})$$

Proof.

$$V = \underline{a} \cdot (\underline{b} \wedge \underline{c}) = \|\underline{a}\| (\underline{b} \wedge \underline{c}) \cos \phi$$

and

$$\|\underline{a}\| \cos \phi = \|\underline{a}_N\|$$

where \underline{a}_N is the component of \underline{a} normal to the plane $\langle \underline{b}, \underline{c} \rangle$, so

$$\|\underline{a}\| \cos \phi = \|\underline{a}_N\| = \|\underline{a} - \underline{a}_b - \underline{a}_c\|$$

where \underline{a}_x is the projection of \underline{a} along \underline{x}

$$\underline{a}_x = \frac{\underline{a} \cdot \underline{x}}{\|\underline{x}\|^2} \underline{x}$$

□

Theorem 3.2. *Volume upper limit.*

$$|V| \leq \|\underline{a}\| (\underline{b} \wedge \underline{c})$$

Proof.

$$|V| = |\underline{a} \cdot (\underline{b} \wedge \underline{c})| = \|\underline{a}\| (\underline{b} \wedge \underline{c}) |\cos \phi| \leq \|\underline{a}\| (\underline{b} \wedge \underline{c})$$

□

Remark 3.1. Since the scalar triple product is unchanged under a circular shift of its three operands ($\underline{a} \cdot (\underline{b} \wedge \underline{c}) = \underline{b} \cdot (\underline{c} \wedge \underline{a}) = \underline{c} \cdot (\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b})$)

$$|V| \leq \min\{\|\underline{a}\| (\underline{b} \wedge \underline{c}), \|\underline{b}\| (\underline{a} \wedge \underline{c}), \|\underline{c}\| (\underline{a} \wedge \underline{b})\}$$

4 Calculus

Theorem 4.1. Given $f : D \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

$$|D^2 f| = \left(\frac{d}{dx} \wedge \frac{d}{dy} \right)^2 f$$

where $D^2 f$ is the Hessian matrix of f , and so $|D^2 f|$ is the Hessian determinant.

Proof.

$$\frac{d}{dx} \wedge \frac{d}{dy} = \sqrt{\begin{vmatrix} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} & \frac{d^2}{dx dy} \\ \frac{d^2}{dx dy} & \frac{d^2}{dy^2} \end{vmatrix}}$$

for Theo. 1.3

$$\left(\frac{d}{dx} \wedge \frac{d}{dy} \right)^2 f = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{d^2 f}{dx^2} & \frac{d^2 f}{dx dy} \\ \frac{d^2 f}{dx dy} & \frac{d^2 f}{dy^2} \end{vmatrix} = |D^2 f|$$

□

5 Scalar area product with signals

Definition 5.1. Scalar area product of signals. Given two signals $x, y \in \mathcal{L}^2$

$$x \wedge y = \sqrt{\|x\|^2 \|y\|^2 - (x \cdot y) \overline{x \cdot y}}$$

like for vectors; where

$$x \cdot y = \mathbb{E}(x \overline{y}) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x(t) \overline{y(t)} dt$$

$$\|x\|^2 = x \cdot x = \mathbb{E}(x \overline{x})$$

Theorem 5.1. Variance. [Does $x \wedge 1$ make sense?]

$$\text{var}(x) = (x \wedge 1)^2$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} (x \wedge 1)^2 &= \|x\|^2 \|1\|^2 - (x \cdot 1) \overline{x \cdot 1} = \|x\|^2 - (x \cdot 1) \overline{x \cdot 1} = \\ &= \mathbb{E}(x \overline{x}) - \mathbb{E}(1x) \overline{\mathbb{E}(1x)} = \mathbb{E}(x \overline{x}) - \mathbb{E}(x) \overline{\mathbb{E}(x)} = \text{var}(x) \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 5.2. *Variance limit.*

$$\text{var}(x + y) \leq \text{var}(x) + \text{var}(y) + 2\sqrt{\text{var}(x)\text{var}(y)}$$

and since $\text{var}(x + y) = \text{var}(x) + \text{var}(y) + 2\text{cov}(x, y)$

$$\text{cov}(x, y) \leq \sqrt{\text{var}(x)\text{var}(y)}$$

which is a known result.

Proof.

$$\text{var}(x + y) = [(x + y) \wedge 1]^2 \leq (x \wedge 1 + y \wedge 1)^2 = \left(\sqrt{\text{var}(x)} + \sqrt{\text{var}(y)} \right)^2$$

□

Theorem 5.3. *Scalar product with unit. [TO CHECK] Given $x \in \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R})$ or $x \in \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{C}) \wedge x \geq 0$*

$$x \cdot 1 = \|\sqrt{x}\|^2$$

Proof.

$$\mathbb{E}(y\bar{y}) = \|y\|^2$$

$$x \cdot 1 = \mathbb{E}(1x) = \mathbb{E}(x)$$

$$1. \ x \in \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}) \implies \mathbb{E}(x) = \mathbb{E}(\sqrt{x^2}) = \mathbb{E}(\sqrt{x}\sqrt{x})$$

$$2. \ x \geq 0 \implies \mathbb{E}(x) = \mathbb{E}(|x|) = \mathbb{E}(\sqrt{x}\sqrt{x})$$

$$\mathbb{E}(\sqrt{x}\sqrt{x}) = \|\sqrt{x}\|^2$$

□

Theorem 5.4. *Scalar area product with unit. [TO CHECK]*

$$x \wedge 1 = \|x - \mathbb{E}(x)\|$$

Proof.

$$\text{var}(x) = \mathbb{E}((x - \mathbb{E}(x))\overline{(x - \mathbb{E}(x))}) = \|x - \mathbb{E}(x)\|^2$$

$$\text{var}(x) = (x \wedge 1)^2 \implies x \wedge 1 = \sqrt{\text{var}(x)}$$

□